

Impact of Leadership Styles on Job Satisfaction among Teachers in Secondary Schools in Monduli District

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to explore the impact of leadership styles on job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district. The study hypotheses were that H₁ there is no statistically significant correlation between transformational leadership style and job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district, H₂ there is no statistically significant correlation between transactional leadership style and job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district and H₃ there is no statistically significant correlation between laissez-faire leadership style and job satisfaction among

teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district.

The study employed a descriptive survey design. A sample size of one hundred twenty-nine respondents was randomly chosen from four secondary schools in Monduli namely; Manyara, Lowassa, Engutoto, and Irkisongo district secondary schools. A self-administered questionnaire was used to collect information from respondents. The collected data were analyzed by Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) using, Independent t-test and Fisher's Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to determine whether demographic variables varied with students' academic performance. Karl Pearson's Linear Correlation Coefficient was undertaken to determine the relationship between leadership styles and teachers' Job satisfaction.

The study results indicated that hypotheses H₁ and H₃ were supported by the study findings. However, the study findings revealed that H₃ was not supported by the study findings. The study concluded that transformational and laissez-faire leadership styles had a direct influence on teachers' job satisfaction. Therefore, school administrators in the Monduli district should use transformational and laissez-faire leadership styles in their day-to-day administration. The study findings led the researcher to recommend that, the school administration should focus on the use of transformational and laissez-faire leadership styles since they had a direct significant influence on teacher's job satisfaction. For future research focus should be on obtaining a larger and more representative sample, conducting the same study in other schools from another district for comparison purposes, and replicating the study using a qualitative approach.

Keywords: *Leadership Styles, Job Satisfaction, Transformational Leadership Style, Transactional Leadership Style, Laissez-faire leadership style.*

Introduction

Job satisfaction has been of interest to organizational researchers, due to its relationship with job performance (Christen, 2006). More importantly, employed individuals spend most of their time doing jobs. As a result, individuals feeling about their jobs are likely to affect those impacting their lives in general (Lim, 2008). Today the issue of teachers' job satisfaction has drawn much attention from society and come up in heated discussion. Teachers' job satisfaction remains a challenge across the globe. Many schools in Africa are notwithstanding this challenge, most of them are characterized by; poor leadership styles growing students' enrolment, inadequate facilities and infrastructures, overwhelming student-teacher ratio, low remuneration, and limited library resources. All these challenges encourage teachers to leave for greener pastures elsewhere Teshome, (2008). Secondary school teachers in Tanzania and in particular, Monduli have not been safe from this challenge.

Several studies on employees' job satisfaction have been conducted by some researchers. For example, (Akhtar 2010) in his study on job satisfaction of secondary school teachers found that female teachers were more satisfied with work and supervision aspects of their job as compared with male teachers further shows no significant difference was found in the job satisfaction between science & arts and urban and rural school teachers. Age and work experience did not explore the job satisfaction difference in teachers. The study by MacMilla (2010) on the influence of workplace conditions on teachers' job satisfaction in Canada, found that workplace conditions positively affected teachers' job satisfaction. Similarly, Addejumo (2012) insists that the job satisfaction status of primary school teachers in Ota, Nigeria found that a greater percentage of teachers (52.9%) were satisfied with their job. Also, Haider (2010) says that the role of transformational and transactional leadership on job satisfaction and career satisfaction found that transformational leadership style and job success are highly related to career satisfaction. Guiled (2013) Leadership styles and job satisfaction empirical evidence

from Mogadishu University found a significant relationship between job satisfaction and transformational leadership style. The study by Yushuang(2013) on the influence of leadership style on job satisfaction among nurses found that the transformational leadership style contributes more toward job satisfaction compared to the transactional leadership style. Despite the considerable body of job satisfaction literature that has involved examining the relationships between leadership styles and employees' job satisfaction in various countries as well as Tanzania, there is no existing study that recognizes leadership styles within the context of Monduli district secondary school teachers, the gap this study sought to fill.

Objective

Specifically, this study was guided by the following objectives:

- i. To examine the impact of transformational leadership style on job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district
- ii. To determine the impact of transactional leadership style on job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district
- iii. To examine the impact of laissez-faire leadership style on job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions

- i. How does transformational leadership style impact job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district?
- ii. How does transactional leadership style impact job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district?
- iii. How does leadership laissez-faire style impact job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested

- i. There is no statistically significant correlation between transformational leadership style and job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district
- ii. There is no statistically significant correlation between transactional leadership style and job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district
- iii. There is no statistically significant correlation between laissez-faire leadership style and job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district

Related Literature

Transformational Leadership

Transformational leaders interact with followers in such a way as to stimulate their thinking, inspire their performance, and perform beyond expectations. Transformational leadership is a process of influencing in which leaders change their associates' awareness of what is important, and move them to see themselves and the opportunities and challenges of their environment in a new way Avolio & Bass (2004). Transformational leadership is the ability to motivate and encourage intellectual stimulation through inspiration.

According to Bass, (1998) transformational leadership is a leadership style that transcends the need for direct tangible rewards and appeals instead to the followers' higher-order needs, inspiring them to act in the best interest of the organization rather than according to their self-interests. Transformational leaders fundamentally change the values, goals, and aspirations of followers who adopt the leader's values and, in the end, perform their work because it is consistent with their values and not because they expect to be rewarded. Transformational leadership which encourages autonomy and challenging work became increasingly important to followers' job

satisfaction. The concept of job security and loyalty to the firm for one's entire career was disappearing. Steady pay, secure benefits, and lifetime employment were no longer guaranteed for meritorious performance. At the same time, transactional leadership alone could not provide job satisfaction.

The study by Bogler (2014) on the influence of leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction found that teacher occupation perception strongly affected their satisfaction. MacMilla (2010) study on the influence of workplace conditions on teacher's job satisfaction in Canada found that workplace conditions positively affected teacher's job satisfaction. Abdullah, (2009) study on job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Tawau, Sabah in Malaysia Relationship between the school principal leadership style and job satisfaction in Serbia, the study found that school principal leadership style influences teachers' satisfaction. Similarly, Adjejumo, (2012) study on the job satisfaction status of primary school teachers in Ota, Nigeria found that a greater percentage of teachers (52.9%) were satisfied with their job. Further, (Haider, 2010) study on the role of transformational and transactional leadership on job satisfaction and career satisfaction found that transformational leadership style and job success are highly related to career satisfaction. Guiled, (2013) study on leadership styles and job satisfaction empirical evidence from Mogadishu University found a significant relationship between job satisfaction and transformational leadership style. Yushuang, (2013) study on the influence of leadership style on job satisfaction among nurses found that the transformational leadership style contributes more toward job satisfaction compared to transactional leadership style.

Emjimofor (2007) in his study the relationship between teachers' perceptions of principals' transformational leadership skills and teachers' job satisfaction. Participants were 518 secondary school teachers and 48 principals from two large Local Government Areas in Southeastern Nigeria. Multiple linear regressions were used to analyze data. It was found that principals' transformational leadership skills significantly

impacted teachers' job satisfaction. Similarly, Ali and Dahile (2015) investigated the impact of transaction leadership style, transformational and laissez-faire on teacher job satisfaction; the study utilized explanatory and descriptive design to analyze 200 respondents from secondary school teachers in Mogadishu, Somalia. The study developed three hypotheses to test the impact of independent variables on dependent variables; to test the hypothesis the researchers utilized regression analysis and checked the outliers and collinearity and no violations were found. The research found that the three dimensions of leadership style had a significant and positive impact on teacher satisfaction in Secondary schools in Mogadishu, Somalia. This study can contribute to assisting school leaders in carrying out leadership activities and give space to teachers to make their own decisions while they are running their teaching work to maintain and enhance the job satisfaction of the teachers in their workplace.

A study conducted in Israel by Bogler (2001) investigated leadership style on teacher job satisfaction in Secondary Schools. It also examines the effects of principals' leadership style, teachers' occupation perceptions on teacher satisfaction from the job, and principals' decision-making strategy. It also tries to find out how much of the variation in teachers' job satisfaction can be attributed to their perceptions of their occupation, as compared to their perceptions of their principals' leadership style. It employed a sample size of 745 teachers. The data was collected quantitative Questionnaire using Likert-type scales. The study found that teachers' occupation Perceptions strongly affected their satisfaction. Principals' transformational leadership affected teachers' job satisfaction both directly and indirectly through their occupation perceptions. Implications of the study are discussed in relation to supervisors and principals, as well as to policymakers at the government level. The model of the study demonstrated that the teachers' perceptions of their principals and their occupations contribute significantly to the explanation of the variance in job satisfaction. However, teachers' perceptions are subjective,

and it may be that their perceptions are affected by variables that were not examined in this study

Research conducted in the region investigated the effects of leadership style on the job satisfaction of teachers among secondary schools in Nakuru District, Kenya; they employed a sample size of 274 teachers. The data was collected a self-structured questionnaires and in-depth interview schedules administered to teachers and head teachers, respectively. The study showed that the dynamic situations in the school environment required head teachers to adopt Different leadership styles. The study contributed to the concerned agencies including the Ministry of Education, school management, teachers and students could use such information to assess the potentials and challenges posed by the leadership styles adopted by head teachers on various aspects of teaching and learning in schools. This may enable them to develop effective strategies that will encourage more participatory leadership styles in schools Karanja, Mugwe, & wanderi (2013).

Verma,(2014) in his study on the effect of leadership styles of principals on the job satisfaction of teachers working in private schools in UAE. The statistical population involved was two hundred and thirty-eight school teachers working in private schools in UAE. Bass and Avolio Multifactor Leadership Style Questionnaires were used to measure the leadership styles of the principals and the Mohrman-Cooke-Mohrman Job Satisfaction Scale instrument was used to measure the job satisfaction of teaching faculties. Descriptive statistics, Pearson Correlation, and Multiple Regression Analysis were employed to analyze the data. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant influence of the transformational leadership styles of principals on the job satisfaction of teachers. (Wahab, Fuad, Ismail, and Majid 2014) study on the level of transformational leadership practices by headmasters in the primary national schools in the district of Temerloh, Malaysia. The four dimensions of Transformational Leadership studied were fostering the ideal influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation,

and individual consideration. The study also looks at the level of teachers' job satisfaction and teachers' commitments as well as the relationship with the practice of transformational leadership by headmasters. The respondents consisted of 240 teachers working in 10 primary schools in the district of Temerloh, Pahang. The data obtained were processed using SPSS program version 12.0 and were analyzed using descriptive and multivariate. The result of the study showed that the practice of transformational leadership by headmasters in the district of Temerloh, Malaysia, was at a high level and teacher's job satisfaction was high too, and there exists a significant relation between the level of transformational leadership and teachers' job satisfaction while teachers' commitments were average. However, the results of the study showed a significant relationship between the level of transformational leadership and teachers' work commitment. This study implies that leaders should always ensure their high-performance leadership to have a significant relationship with staff's satisfaction and school staff's commitment.

Transactional Leadership

Transactional leaders focus their energies on task completion and compliance and rely on organizational rewards and punishments to influence employee performance, with rewards being contingent on the followers for carrying out the roles and assignments as defined by the leader (Bass & Avolio, 2004). Many times, transactional leadership is viewed as an exchange process in which the leader provides rewards to followers in the form of pay or prestige in exchange for work done by the follower (Burns 1978). Also referred to as "contingent reward leadership, transactional leadership is considered to be both an active and positive exchange between the leader and follower" (Brymer 2006). Transactional leadership relies on the use of appropriate rewards to motivate followers (Pearce, 2002). Also, it focuses and emphasizes on completion and accomplishing of allocated tasks on hand. This type of leader maintains and preserves harmonious working relationships

coupled with promises of rewards for satisfactory performance.

Furthermore, this leadership focuses on leader-follower exchanges in which followers or subordinates are expected to carry out his or her duties and perform according to the given instructions. Interpreted as a non-transactional kind of leadership style in which prompt decisions are not made with delay in action taken, coupled with ignoring of leadership responsibility and non-exercise of authority (Huberts, et al, (2007). Principal transformational leadership affects teachers' job satisfaction both directly and indirectly through their occupation perception.

Several researchers had an interest in leadership style as correlates with employee job satisfaction. For example, Demissie, (2013) relationship between leadership styles of nurse managers and nurses' job satisfaction in Jimma University specialized hospital found that transactional leadership, only contingent reward was found to be statically significant and correlated with extrinsic ($B=0.45$, $p<0.01$) and intrinsic job satisfaction ($B=0.32$, $p<0.05$) while all five dimensions of transformational leadership style were statistically significant and correlated with both intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction. Similarly, Rahim, (2014) leadership styles and employees Job Satisfaction in the Private Banking Sector of Pakistan found that there is a significant relationship between transactional leadership style and employees' job satisfaction, and this transactional leadership style is more adopted by leaders as compared to transformational leadership style. Further, Waquas, et al.(2012) impact of leadership style (transformational & transactional leadership) on employee performance & mediating role of job satisfaction study of private schools (educators) in Pakistan found that transactional and transformational both are significantly and positively associated with Employee performance however transactional leadership was more significant than transformational. Another important discovery made was there is no mediating role of Job satisfaction between transactional leadership.

Hlanganipai (2014) shows the impact of leadership styles on employee organizational commitment in higher learning institutions and finds that transactional leadership style has a significant and positive relationship with only normative commitment. Afshipour (2014) leadership styles and employee satisfaction, a correlation study in the USA found that transactional leadership style has a positive correlation with employee job satisfaction.

Nyenyembe, Malsowski, Nimrod & Peter (2016) in their study on the relationship between leadership styles applied by school heads and teachers' job satisfaction in Tanzanian secondary schools, using a questionnaire, data in this study was collected from 180 teachers in ten secondary schools in Songea District in Tanzania. The most salient finding of this study revealed that teachers were more satisfied with their jobs when their school heads worked closely with them by mentoring them as well as paying attention to their well-being. Kashagate, (2013) study on the effects of leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Musoma Municipal Council, the study examines whether transformational and transactional leadership styles stimulate and sustain teachers' job satisfaction. Questionnaires were administered to 54 public secondary school teachers from different schools. The Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) and the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) were used by teachers to assess their heads of schools in relation to the satisfaction they derive from their jobs. To analyse the data, multiple regression analyses were conducted to examine how well transformational and transactional leadership factors predict teachers' job satisfaction. Overall the results of the present study yielded some significant findings. The results showed a positive correlation between transformational leadership dimensions on teachers' job satisfaction. With regard to transactional leadership dimensions, the results showed that transactional leadership affects the outcome variable, but their influence was lower as compared to the influence of transformational leadership factors. The individual transactional leadership factors that had positively influenced

the outcome variable were Contingent rewards and active management by exception. Bass and Avolio (2004) found that transactional leadership can be extremely effective. However, if both transactional and transformational leadership are used together, there is a greater amount of effort given from the followers, and there is in turn higher workplace effectiveness and higher teacher job satisfaction.

Laissez-faire Leadership Style

Laissez-faire leadership is a passive kind of leadership style. This type of leader generally gives his or her followers or employees complete freedom to make decisions or to complete a task in whichever way they deem fit and appropriate (Robbins et al., 2010). It is also being interpreted as a non-transactional kind of leadership style in which prompt decisions are not made with delay in action taken, coupled with ignoring of leadership responsibilities and non-exercise of authority. Two researchers agreed on the behaviors and management practices of a laissez-faire leader Northouse, (2013; Schilling, 2009). First, a leader's behavior of keeping a distance from the leadership role occurs when there are no scheduled meetings. Secondly, leaders practice the hands-off approach when avoiding decision-making. Third, a leader shows the behavior of giving up responsibilities when little contact occurs with employees. Fourth, a leader shows the behavior of displaying indifference to the needs of followers, when no effort to help followers satisfy needs occurs. Despite the commonly agreed-upon characteristics of the laissez-faire leader, research findings revealed that there is effectiveness in using laissez-faire leadership when used in combination with transformational and transactional leadership styles (Pihie & Sadeghi, 2012;). Pihie & Sadeghi's, quantitative study (2012) included academic deans that utilized the laissez-faire leadership style that was appropriate in the situation because the employees desired to operate with autonomy.

Hamidifar (2010) commented that leaders who practice this leadership style usually do not care and take no consideration and concern for issues that arise in the organization's environment.

Laissez-faire refers to the "hands-off, let things ride" approach in its original French phrase. Leaders of Laissez-Faire are said to relinquish responsibility, give no feedback, delay decision-making, and not be keen to help followers in satisfying their needs (Northouse, 2010). Some researchers attempted to conduct studies on job satisfaction as correlates to employee job satisfaction. For example, (Hassan, 2014) tested the impact of leadership styles on employee performance: A study by the Department of Petroleum Resources found that a laissez-faire leadership style has tested has positive relationship with the performance of employees. Moreover, (Stale, et al 2014) the relative effects of constructive, laissez-faire, and tyrannical leadership on subordinate job satisfaction, results from two prospective and representative studies found that laissez-faire leadership was the sole predictor of job satisfaction over a 2-year time lag. (Adeyemi 2010) leadership style and job satisfaction in Nigerian schools found that there was no significant relationship between principals' laissez-faire leadership style and teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. (Dalhie 2015) Leadership and leaders' job satisfaction in Somalia secondary schools found that laissez-faire had a significant and positive impact on teachers' satisfaction in secondary schools in Mogadishu, Somalia.

Research Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive survey design. This design was used in collecting information by administering questionnaires to a sample of the population which consists of head teachers and teachers. Both the quantitative and qualitative approaches was used. The questionnaires were used to collect quantitative data and interviews to collect qualitative data (Sarantakos, 2001).

Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

Given the time and limited financial resources for this study, the researcher was not able to collect data from all teachers from public

secondary schools all accessible teachers in Monduli district, and a sample of the population was drawn. According to Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table of sample size(s) determination, it is suggested that if one has a population of size, $N = 200$ units, one needs a minimum sample size of, $s = 132$. Therefore, for this proposed study the researcher will use a sample of 132 teachers in Monduli district. The population of teachers was divided into four secondary schools (strata) which were homogenous internally but heterogeneous from one to another. The sample of 132 teachers was allocated equally to each of the four strata.

Data Collection Methods

Data was collected from respondents by using self-administered questionnaires. The descriptive survey method was used to gather data from a sample of the population at a particular time Amin(2005). This was done to find out the opinions, preferences, and attitudes, concerns of a cross-section of the population about leadership style and job satisfaction. Interviews were also conducted to give free responses by subjects from whom the researcher gathered more perspectives

Data Analysis, Presentation, and Interpretation Plan

After collecting the filled questionnaires, the researcher analyzed the data using descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics results were presented in the form of percentages, means, standard deviations, and frequencies. All numerical variables such as the total index on transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire analysis are univariate, targeting one variable at a time. Inferential data analysis was used; and bivariate analysis to test the hypothesis of correlating each numerical independent variable with a numerical dependent variable using Karl Pearson's Linear Correlation Coefficient. Also, multivariate regression was conducted to reveal the contribution of each variable (transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire) to the prediction of job satisfaction. Finally, data will be presented and interpreted, and conclusions and

recommendations will be drawn based on the used by analyzed data.

Validity of the Research Instrument

According to Sarandakos (2001), validity shows the accuracy and meaningfulness of inferences that are based on the research results. In other words, validity is the degree to which results obtained from the analysis of the data represent the phenomenon under study. The research instrument was piloted on a sample to find out if everything works well and detect any potential misunderstanding or biasing effects of different questions. The pilot study helped the researcher to improve the face validity and content of the instruments. Also, the content Validity Index (CVI) was computed.

Reliability of the Research Instrument

To ensure the reliability of research instruments, the researcher will compute the Cronbach Alpha coefficient. According to McMillan (2006), Cronbach's alpha greater than 0.7 (>0.7) indicates the reliability of the instrument. Cronbach's alpha determines the extent to which the contents of the questionnaire are consistent in producing the same response every time the instrument is administered. Therefore, the researcher established the reliability of the instrument using Cronbach's alpha coefficient.

Background Information of the Respondents

The initial section of the instrument asked the respondents to respond to the five background variables: Sex, age, marital status, current highest education level, and the nature of the job.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents by Sex

Sex	Number of Teachers	Percentage	Cumulative Percent
Female	39	30.2	30.2
Male	90	69.8	100.0
Total	129	100.0	

Table 1 shows that almost 70% of respondents were male. This suggests that the majority of teachers were male in the surveyed secondary schools in Monduli district. This male

dominance can be attributed to a culture of majority ethnic groups in Tanzania who favor the provision of education for boys than girls.

Table 2. Distribution of Respondents by Age Group

Age group (years)	Number of Teachers	Percentage	Cumulative Percent
15 – 21	3	2.3	2.3
22 – 28	71	55.0	57.4
29 – 34	36	27.9	85.3
35 – 41	15	11.9	96.9
42 +	4	3.1	100.00
Total	129	100.0	

Table .2 shows that 55% of respondents fall within 22 - 28 age group, 27.8% of the respondents fall within 29- 34 age group, 11.9% of respondents fall under 35 – 41 age group, 3.1% of respondents fall within 42+ age group and 2.3% of respondents fall under 15- 21 age

group. This 85.3% suggests that the majority of teachers in the surveyed secondary schools were young and can work for a teaching professional for a long time before reached retirement age which is 60 years for government employees.

Table 3. Distribution of Respondents by Marital Status

Marital status	Number of teachers	Percentage	Cumulative Percent
Single	62	48.1	48
Married	65	50.4	98.4
Separated	2	1.6	100.0
Total	129	100.0	

Table 3 shows that 50.4% of respondents were married. This suggests the majority of the teachers (50.4%) were married. This is not surprising considering that by the time one

graduated and employed, one is matured to be married. This could explain why the majority were married.

Table 4. Distribution of Respondents by Level of Education

Education qualification	Number of teachers	Percentage	Cumulative Percent
Diploma	34	26.4	26.4
Degree	84	65.1	91.5
Masters	11	8.5	100.0
Total	129	100.0	

Table 4 displays that 65.1% of the respondents had a bachelor's degree. This means that the majority of teachers in the surveyed secondary

schools in Monduli district were qualified to teach secondary school students.

Table 5. Distribution of Respondents by Nature of their Job

Nature of the job	Number of teachers	Percentage	Cumulative Percent
Permanent	105	81.4	81.4
Contract	17	13.2	94.6
Part time	7	5.4	100.0
Total	129	100.0	

According to Table 5 majority of the respondents 81.4% were permanently employed. This means that most of the respondents were employed on permanent terms of services in the surveyed secondary schools in Monduli district.

job, using Likert's five point scale ranging from one which represented by very dissatisfied, two represented dissatisfied, three represented neutral, four represented satisfied and five represented very satisfied. Table 6 displays pertinent means and standard deviations:

Description of the Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

The respondents were asked to rate themselves in terms of how they were satisfied with their

Table 6. Respondent Self-Rating on Job Satisfaction

Indicator	Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very satisfied	Mean	Remarks
The praise I got for doing a good job	16 12.4%	9 7.0%	24 18.6%	55 42.6%	25 19.4%	3.496	Good
I am valued as individual by my head teacher	5 3.9%	15 11.6%	16 12.4%	73 56.6%	20 15.5%	3.682	Good

Respect I receive from my co-workers	8 6.2%	4 3.1%	19 14.7%	58 45.0%	40 31.0%	3.914	Good
The way my co-workers support me	5 3.9%	7 5.4%	24 18.6%	57 44.2%	36 27.9%	3.868	Good
The opportunities available for my professional growth	5 3.9%	20 15.5%	27 20.9%	58 45.0%	19 14.7%	3.511	Good
The chances for promotion available for me	13 10.1%	17 13.2%	27 20.9%	51 39.5%	21 16.3%	3.387	Good

Concerning the praise I got for doing a good job, Table 4.6 shows that 19.4% of teachers rated themselves as either very dissatisfied or dissatisfied as opposed to other counterparts with a high rate of 62% who rated themselves as either satisfied or very satisfied. This fair rating is confirmed by a high mean 3.496 corresponding to satisfaction with the praise I got for doing a good job. Regarding the way I am valued as an individual by my head teacher; Table 4.6 shows that 15.5% of respondents rated themselves as either very dissatisfied or dissatisfied as opposed to other counterparts with as high as 72.1% in the category of satisfied or very satisfied. This good rating is confirmed by a high mean of 3.682 corresponding to highly valued teachers received from the head teacher. Regarding the respect I receive from my co-workers, Table 4.6 shows that 9.3% of teachers rated themselves as either very dissatisfied or dissatisfied as opposed to their counterparts with a higher rate of 76% who rated themselves as either satisfied or very satisfied. This good rating is confirmed by a relatively high mean of 3.914 corresponding to good respect from co-workers. Regarding the way my co-workers support me, Table 6 shows that 9.3 % of respondents rated

themselves as either very dissatisfied or dissatisfied as opposed to their counterparts with high 72.1% who rated themselves as either satisfied or very satisfied. This good rating is confirmed by a relatively high mean of 3.868 corresponding to good support from co-workers. About the opportunities available for my professional growth, Table 6 shows that 19.4% of respondents rated themselves as either very dissatisfied or dissatisfied as opposed to other counterparts with as high as 59.7% who rated themselves as either satisfied or very satisfied. This good rating is confirmed by a high mean of 3.511 corresponding to plant chances for professional growth available in the surveyed secondary schools in Monduli district. Looking at the item “The chances for promotion available for me,” Table 6 exposes that high mean value of 3.387 signifying that teachers in the surveyed secondary schools in Monduli district were fairly satisfied with their chances for promotion in place. To give an overall picture of how teachers rated themselves on job satisfaction, an average index (“Jobsat” to imply job satisfaction) was computed from the six statements in Table 6 and Table 7 giving pertinent descriptive statistics:

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics of the Respondents' Self-Rating on Job Satisfaction

Statistics		Value
Mean		3.643
95% confidence interval	Lower bound	3.507
	Upper bound	3.779
Minimum		1.33
Maximum		5.00
Range		3.67

Table 7 shows that the mean value 3.643 with a confidence interval of 3.507 to 3.779 at the 95 % level corresponding with fair job satisfaction.

Table 7 reveals that some teachers scored very poor is a minimum 1.33 though others scored

best is a maximum of 5.00. This gave a wide gap as reflected by a high range of 3.67.

Variations of Dependent Variable with Background Variables in the Study

In this section, the researcher was interested in finding out whether job satisfaction varied by sex, age, marital status, education level, and the nature of the job of respondents.

Variation of Job Satisfaction with Sex of Respondent

This section is interested in establishing whether the sex of the respondent has a relationship with one's job satisfaction. Table 8 shows t-test results in a variation of job satisfaction among males and females in the surveyed secondary schools in Monduli district.

Table 8. Descriptive Statistics and Student t - test on how Sex Relates to Job Satisfaction

Sex	Frequency	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Sig
Male	90	3.690	0.758	-1.003	0.750
Female	39	3.534	0.836		

According to the means in Table 8 job satisfaction of teachers differed slightly with the sex of the respondent with males having high job satisfaction (mean = 3.690) than females (mean = 3.534). Also, Table 8 indicates t- a value -1.003 whose sign = 0.750 which is greater than popular $\alpha = 0.05$. This implies that sex of the respondent did not differ significantly from one's job

satisfaction level at five percent level of significance.

Variation of Job Satisfaction with Age of Respondents

Table .9 gives the descriptive statistics and ANOVA results on the variation of job satisfaction with respondent age groups:

Table 9. Descriptive Statistics and ANOVA on how Job Satisfaction Relates to the Age of the Respondent

Age group	Frequency	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig
15 – 21	3	3.555	0.509		
22 – 28	71	3.575	0.837	0.718	0.582
29 – 34	36	3.533	0.749		
35 – 41	15	3.666	0.658		
41+	4	3.643	0.652		
Total	129	3.643	0.782		

The means in Table 9 suggest that job satisfaction differed based on respondents' ages. Teachers age group 42+ had the highest level of job satisfaction (mean = 3.643), followed by those in the age group between 35- 41 years (mean = 3.666). Those in the age group of 22- 28 had (mean = 3.575). Age group of 15 – 21 and 29- 34 had low (mean = 3.555 and 3.533 respectively) suggesting a low level of job satisfaction. However, the F value was 0.718 with a Sig = 0.582 which is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$

meaning that job satisfaction did not differed significantly with the age group of teachers at the five percent level of significance.

Variation of Job Satisfaction with Respondent Marital Status

The research grouped respondents into four marital statuses: single, married, divorced, and separated. Table 10 displays descriptive statistics and ANOVA results on the variation of job satisfaction with the respondent marital status.

**Table 10. Descriptive Statistics and ANOVA
on how Job satisfaction Varies with one's Marital Status**

Marital status	Frequency	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig
Single	62	3.698	0.716	0.601	0.550
Married	65	3.605	0.850		
Separate	2	3.166	0.235		
Total	129	3.643	0.782		

The means in Table 10 indicate that job satisfaction was highest among single respondents (mean = 3.698) followed by married (mean = 3.605) and separate respondents (3.166). However, to establish the value is 0.601 with a Sig = 0.550. Since Sig was greater than $\alpha = 0.05$ then one's marital status did differ significantly from the job satisfaction level of the teachers in the surveyed secondary schools in Monduli district at the five percent level of significance.

Variation of Job Satisfaction with Respondent's Education Level

The researcher investigated how education level of teachers varied with job satisfaction. Descriptive statistics and ANOVA results for variation of job satisfaction with the education level of the teachers in the surveyed secondary schools in Monduli district shown in Table 11:

**Table 11. Descriptive Statistics and ANOVA
on how Job Satisfaction Varies with Respondent Educational Level**

Education level	Frequency	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig
Bachelor's degree	84	3.656	0.792	0.674	0.929
Master's degree	11	3.560	0.708		
Diploma	34	3.637	0.800		
Total	129	3.643	0.782		

According to Table 11 means suggest that a high level of satisfaction among teachers who had a bachelor's degree (mean = 3.656) and slightly different among those who had a master's degree and a diploma (mean = 3.560 and 3.637) respectively. The F value 0.674 was considered a significant relationship whose Sig = 0.929 which is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$. Hence, this means that the respondent's level of education did not differ significantly from job satisfaction at the five percent level of significance.

Variation of Job Satisfaction with the Nature of the Job of the Respondent

In this part, the researcher established the relationship between job satisfaction and the nature of the job of the respondents. To achieve this, the researcher requested respondents to state whether they were on permanent, contract, or part-time employment. Table 12 gives descriptive statistics and ANOVA results:

**Table 12. Descriptive Statistics and ANOVA
on how job satisfaction Varies with the Nature of the Job of the Respondent**

Category of nature of the job	Frequency	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig
Permanent	105	3.655	0.784	0.276	0.760
Contract	17	3.656	0.602		
Part time	7	3.428	1.177		
Total	129	3.643	0.782		

Means is Table 12 suggests that the teachers' level of job satisfaction different from the nature of the job. Teachers in contract employment had the highest job satisfaction level (means = 3.656) than those in permanent (mean = 3.655) and part-time employment (mean = 3.428). The F value was 0.276 and its Sig = 0.760 which is far greater than $\alpha = 0.05$ implying that the nature of the job did not differ significantly with the job satisfaction level of the teachers in the surveyed secondary schools in Monduli district at the five percent level of significance.

Description of Independent Variables

Transformational Leadership Style

Transformational leadership style was the first independent variable in the study with six items whereby respondents rated themselves on the five aspects based on Likert's five-point scale ranging from 1 = Strongly disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Undecided, 4 = Agree and 5 = Strongly agree. Table 13 shows pertinent tables and means.

Table 13. Teachers Responses on Transformational Leadership Style

Indicators	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly agree	Mean	Remarks
My head teacher needs high performance in my work	6 4.7%	5 3.9%	3 2.3%	60 46.5%	55 42.6	4.186	Good
My head teacher supported me	1 0.8%	14 10.9%	15 11.6%	68 52.7%	31 24%	3.883	Good
My head teacher stimulates my intellectual curiosity	8 6.2%	12 9.3%	18 14%	72 55.8%	19 14.7%	3.635	Good
My head teacher waits for things to go wrong before taking action	33 25.6%	21 16.3%	33 25.6%	31 24%	11 8.5%	2.736	Fair
My head teacher takes enthusiastically about what needs to accomplish	10 7.8%	8 6.2%	33 25.6%	65 50.4%	13 10.1%	3.488	Good
My head teacher specifies the importance of having sense of purpose	5 3.9%	10 7.8%	23 17.8%	65 50.4%	26 20.2%	3.751	Good

Table 13 the findings show that 89.1% of teachers rated themselves as either strongly agree or agree as opposed to other counterparts with a lower rate of 8.6% who rated themselves as either strongly disagree or disagree. This rating is confirmed by a high mean 4.186(good) corresponding to high performance of teachers in surveyed secondary schools. Concerning my head teacher support me; Table 13 shows that 76.7% of respondents rated themselves as either strongly agree or agree as opposed to other counterparts with as low as 11.7% in the category of strongly disagree or disagree. This good rating is confirmed by a relatively high mean of 3.883(good). This indicates that teachers were well supported. Regarding my head teacher stimulates my intellectual curiosity, Table 13 shows that 15.5% of teachers rated

themselves as either strongly disagree or disagree as opposed to their counterparts with a high rate of 70.5% who rated themselves as either strongly agree or agree. This fair rating is confirmed by a relatively fair mean of 3.635 corresponding to fair stimulation of intellectual curiosity. Regarding my head teacher waits for things to go wrong before taking action, Table 13 shows that 29.5 % of respondents rated themselves as either strongly agree or agree as opposed to their counterparts with fur high 41.9% who rated themselves as either strongly disagree or disagree. This fair rating is confirmed by a relatively fair mean of 2.736 corresponding to fair action taken. Regarding my head teacher takes enthusiasm about what needs to be accomplished, Table 13 shows that 60.5% of respondents rated themselves as either strongly

agree or agree as opposed to other counterparts with as low as 14% who rated themselves as either strongly disagree or disagree. This good rating is confirmed by a high mean 3.488 corresponding to ardently taken of what needs to be accomplished. Regarding my head teacher specifying the importance of having a sense of purpose, Table 13 also shows that 70.6% of teachers rated themselves as either strongly agree or agree as opposed to other counterparts with a

lower rate 11.7% in the category of either strongly disagree or disagree. This fair rating is confirmed by a relatively good mean of 3.751 corresponding to a good sense of purpose in place. To have an overall picture of how teachers rated themselves on transformational leadership style an average index (transform) was computed from six items in Table 13 and Table 14 gives pertinent descriptive statistics:

Table 14. Descriptive Statistics on Respondents' Transformational Leadership Style

Statistics		Value
Mean		3.613
95% confidence interval	Lower bound	3.503
	Upper bound	3.723
Minimum		1.50
Maximum		5.00
Range		3.50

According to Table 14 mean values were 3.613 with a confidence interval of 3.503 to 3.723 at the 95% level corresponding with a fair rating of transformational leadership style. Table 14 reveals that some teachers scored poorly is a minimum 1.50 while others scored best that is a maximum of 5.00. This gave a wide difference as mirrored by a high range of 3.50. The fair rating regarding transformational leadership style in the surveyed secondary schools in Monduli is also supported by the views obtained qualitatively. For example, head teachers responded to the question "how do you communicate with your teacher" as follows:

"I communicate with my teacher through memos, meetings, and announcements," I communicate with my teacher through staff meetings, and their responsibilities," I

communicate with my teachers through general meetings, departmental meetings, and in writings." Also, "I prefer transformational leadership style than another leadership style"

Such views clearly show that head teachers prefer a transformational leadership style in their day-to-day administration.

Transactional Leadership Style

Transactional leadership style was the second independent variable in the study with six items whereby respondents rated themselves on the five aspects based on Likert's five-point scale ranging from 1 = Strongly disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Undecided, 4 = Agree and 5 = Strongly agree. Table 15 shows pertinent tables and means:

Table 15. Teachers Responses on Transactional Leadership Style

Indicators	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly agree	Mean	Remarks
My head teacher rewards for good work done	7 5.4%	12 9.3%	20 15.5%	57 44.2%	33 25.6%	3.751	Good
My head teacher provides punishment for bad work done	3 2.3%	20 15.5%	22 17.1%	58 45%	26 20.2%	3.651	Good
My head teacher articulate a compelling vision of the future	4 3.1%	8 6.2%	32 24.8%	64 49.6%	21 16.3%	3.697	Good

My head teacher focuses attention on mistakes and deviation from standards	9 7%	7 7.4%	25 19.4%	69 53.5%	19 14.7%	3.635	Good
My head teacher goes beyond self-interest for the good of the school	9 7%	12 9.3%	32 24.8%	51 39.5%	25 19.4%	3.550	Good
My head teacher specifies the importance of having a strong sense of purpose	8 6.2%	3 2.3%	17 13.2%	62 48.1%	39 30.2%	3.938	Good

Table 15 shows that 14.7 % of respondents rated themselves as either strongly disagree or disagree as opposed to other counterparts with a high rate of 89.8% who rated themselves as either strongly agree or agree. This rating is confirmed by mean 3.751(good). This finding shows that the teachers were rewarded for a good job done. Looking at my head teacher articulates a compelling vision of the future; Table 15 shows that 17.8% of respondents rated themselves as either strongly disagree or disagree as opposed to other counterparts with as high as 65.2% in the category of strongly agree or agree. This fair rating is confirmed by a relatively good mean of 3.651 corresponding to fair punishment for bad work. Concerning my head teacher articulating a compelling vision of the future, Table 15 shows that 9.3% of teachers rated themselves as either strongly disagree or disagree as opposed to their counterparts with a high rate of 65.2 % who rated themselves as either strongly agree or agree. This fair rating is confirmed by a relatively high mean of 3.697 corresponding to good articulation of a compelling vision. About my head teacher focus attention on mistake and deviation from standards, Table 15 shows that 12.4% of respondents rated themselves as either strongly disagree or disagree as opposed to their

counterparts with fur high 68.2% who rated themselves as either strongly agree or agree. This fair rating is confirmed by a relatively fair mean of 3.635 corresponding to good attention to mistakes and deviation from standards. Regarding my head teacher going beyond self-interest for the good of the school, Table 15 shows that 16.3% of respondents rated themselves as either strongly disagree or disagree as opposed to other counterparts with as high 58.9% in the category of strongly agree or agree. This fair rating is confirmed by a high mean of 3.550 corresponding to good school interest. Looking at my head teacher specifying the importance of having a strong sense of purpose, Table 15 shows that 8.5% of respondents rated themselves as either strongly disagree or disagree as opposed to other counterparts with as high as 78.3% in the category of strongly agree or agree. This fair rating is confirmed by a relatively good mean of 3.938 corresponding to good specification of sense of purpose. To give an overall picture of how teachers on surveyed secondary schools rated themselves on transactional leadership style an average index (“Transaction” to imply transactional leadership style) was computed. Table 15 and Table 16 give descriptive statistics:

Table 16. Descriptive Statistics on Teachers’ Responses on Transactional Leadership Style

Statistics		Value
Mean		3.704
95% confidence interval	Lower bound	3.593
	Upper bound	3.815
Minimum		2.17
Maximum		5.00
Range		2.83

From Table 16 it is inferred that teacher self-rating on transactional leadership style was good

shown by a mean value of 3.704 with a confidence interval ranging from 3.593 to 3.815

at the 95% level. Table 16 also shows that some teachers scored poor that is minimum 2.17 while others scored best is a maximum of 5.00. This gave a slight gap as revealed by a range of 2.83. The fair rating regarding transactional leadership style in the surveyed secondary school in Monduli district is also supported by the views obtained qualitatively.

"I support my subordinates in different aspects for example by providing them with teaching and learning resources as well as advice on different matters," "The support I provide to my subordinates is helpful and enough for the implementation of their duties," I provide good support to my teachers."

Below are some of the negative views regarding the transformational leadership style, "most of my subordinates do not have intellectual curiosity because they cannot do their work effectively until they are commanded and instructed to do so".

Laissez-faire Leadership Style

Laissez-faire leadership style was the third independent variable in the study with six items whereby respondents rated themselves on the five aspects based on Likert's five-point scale ranging from 1 = Strongly disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Undecided, 4 = Agree and 5 = Strongly agree. Table 17 shows pertinent tables and means:

Table 17. Teachers Responses on Laissez-faire Leadership Style

Indicators	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly agree	Mean	Remarks
My head teacher waits for things to go wrong before taking action	46 35.7%	21 16.3%	22 17.1%	21 16.3%	19 14.7%	2.581	Fair
My head teacher do not support me	42 32.6%	37 28.7%	17 13.2%	21 16.3%	12 9.3%	2.410	Poor
My head teacher avoids getting involve when important issues arise	39 30.2%	27 20.9%	22 17.1%	26 20.2%	15 11.6%	2.620	Fair
My head teacher fails to interfere until the problem became serious	45 34.9%	25 19.4%	23 17.8%	25 19.4%	11 8.5%	2.472	Poor
My head teacher let subordinates to decide on him/her	30 23.3%	29 22.5%	24 18.6%	28 21.7%	18 14%	2.806	Fair
My head teacher is not afraid of poor performance of the teacher	45 34.9%	33 25.6%	18 14%	18 14%	15 11.6%	2.418	Poor

Table 17 shows that 52% of respondents rated themselves as either strongly disagree or disagree as opposed to other counterparts with as low as 31% who rated themselves as either strongly agree or agree. This fair rating is confirmed by a fair mean of 2.410 corresponding to fair action taken before things went wrong. Regarding my head teacher does not support me, Table 17 shows that 61.3% of respondents rated themselves as either strongly disagree or disagree as opposed to other counterparts with as low as 25.6% in the category of either strongly agree or agree. This poor rating is confirmed by a relatively poor mean of 2.410 corresponding to poor support from the head teacher. Concerning my head teacher avoiding getting involved when important issues arise, Table 17

shows that 51.1% of respondents rated themselves as either strongly disagree or disagree as opposed to their counterparts with as low as 31.8% who rated themselves as either strongly agree or agree. This fair rating is confirmed by a relatively fair mean of 2.620 corresponding to fair involvement in important issues in the surveyed secondary schools. About my head teacher failing to interfere until the problem became serious, Table 17 shows that 54.3 % of respondents rated themselves as strongly disagree or disagree as opposed to their counterparts with very lower 27.9 % who rated themselves as either strongly agree or agree. This fair rating is confirmed by a relatively poor mean of 2.472 corresponding to fair interference of the problem. About my head teacher letting

subordinates to decide on him/her; Table 17 shows that 45.8% of respondents rated themselves as either strongly disagree or disagree as opposed to their counterparts with very lower as 35.7% who rated themselves as either strongly agree or agree. This fair rating is confirmed by a relatively fair mean of 2.806 corresponding to fair decisions from subordinates. Concerning my head teacher is not afraid of poor performance of teacher, Table 17 shows that 60.5% of respondents rated themselves as either strongly agree or agree as opposed to their counterparts

with very lower as 25% who rated themselves as disagree or disagree. This poor rating is confirmed by a relatively poor mean of 2.418 corresponding to poor afraid of poor performance of teachers. To give an overall picture of how teachers in surveyed secondary schools rated themselves on laissez-faire leadership style an average index ("Laissez" to imply laissez-faire leadership style) was computed. Table 17 and Table 18 give descriptive statistics:

Table 18. Descriptive Statistics on Teachers' Responses to Laissez-faire Leadership Style

Statistics		Value
Mean		2.578
95% confidence interval	Lower bound	2.588
	Upper bound	2.769
Minimum		1.00
Maximum		5.00
Range		4.00

From Table 18 it is inferred that teacher self-rating on laissez-faire leadership style was fair shown by a mean value of 2.578 with a confidence interval ranging from 2.588 to 2.769 at the 95% level. Table 18 also shows that some teachers scored poor with is minimum 1.00 while others scored best is a maximum of 5.00. This gave a wide gap as revealed by a range of 4.00. The fair rating regarding transactional leadership style in the surveyed secondary school in Monduli district is also supported by the views obtained qualitatively. For example, some head teachers responded to the question "how would you intervene in misunderstanding among teachers" as follows:

"I intervene in misunderstanding among teachers by providing warning, advice and sometimes punishment to the wrongdoer," By having openness and free discussion on issues that bring misunderstanding to the staff," I use dialog for solving misunderstanding among staff."

Such a view clearly shows that head teachers were fairly use laissez-faire leadership style.

Preliminary Testing of Hypotheses

This section deals with the testing of three study hypotheses and presents the results on how independent variables: transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style, and laissez-faire leadership style relate to the dependent variable job satisfaction.

Hypothesis One

One hypothesis of the study stated that "there is no statistically significant correlation between transformational leadership style and job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district." To test this, transformational leadership style the two numerical indices (Transform and Jobsat) were correlated using Pearson's Linear Correlation index. Table 19 gives the pertinent results:

Table 19. Pearson's Linear Correlation between Transformational Leadership Style a Job Satisfaction

		Job Satisfaction	Transformational
Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	0.441(**)
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	129	129
Transformational	Pearson Correlation	0.441(**)	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	129	129

Note: **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

According to Table 19 the correlation between transformational leadership style and job satisfaction using Persons linear correlation coefficient gave $r = 0.441$ and its Sig = 0.000 which is far less than $\alpha = 0.05$. The computed Sig (0.000) suggests that transformational leadership style and job satisfaction were positively linearly correlated, thus preliminary acceptance of the research hypothesis that, transformational leadership style was positively statistically significantly correlated with job satisfaction among teachers in the surveyed secondary schools in Monduli district at the five percent level of significance. This study finding corresponds with findings by Bogler (2014), MacMilla (2010), Abdullah (2009) and Adjejumo

(2012) who reported that transformational leadership style and job success are highly related to career satisfaction.

Hypothesis Two

The second hypothesis in the study was that “there is no statistically significant correlation between transactional leadership style and job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district.” Using responses under transactional leadership style only, the two numerical variables (Transaction and Jobsat) were correlated using Pearson's linear correlation coefficient as shown in Table 20:

Table 20. Pearson's Linear Correlation between Transactional Leadership Style and Job Satisfaction

		Job Satisfaction	Transactional
Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	0.323(**)
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	129	129
Transactional	Pearson Correlation	0.323(**)	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	129	129

Note: ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Results in Table 20 show that the correlation between transactional leadership style and job satisfaction using Pearson's linear correlation coefficient statistics indicated $r = 0.323$ whose Sig = 0.000 which is far less than popular $\alpha = 0.05$ suggesting preliminary acceptance of the research hypothesis that transactional leadership style was positively statistically significant

correlated with employee job satisfaction in the surveyed secondary schools in Monduli district at five level of significance. Waquas, et al. (2012), Hlanganipai (2014) and Afshipour (2014) found similar relationships in their analysis that transactional leadership style has a positive correlation with employee job satisfaction.

Hypothesis Three

The third hypothesis in the study was “there is no statistically significant correlation between laissez-faire leadership style and job satisfaction

among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district ” To confirm this, the two variables (Laissez and Jobsat) were correlated using Pearson’s linear correlation as in Table 21:

Table 21. Pearson’s Linear Correlation between Laissez-faire Leadership Style and Job Satisfaction

		Job Satisfaction	Laissez-faire
Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.159
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.072
	N	129	129
Laissez-faire	Pearson Correlation	-0.159	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.072	
	N	129	129

According to Table 21 the correlation between laissez-faire leadership style and job satisfaction using Persons linear correlation coefficient gave $r = -0.159$ and its $Sig = 0.072$ which was greater than $\alpha = 0.05$ suggesting preliminary acceptance of the null hypothesis that there is no positively statistically significant correlation between laissez-faire leadership style and job satisfaction among teachers in the surveyed secondary schools in Monduli district at five level of significance. This study finding corresponds with the findings by Hassan (2014) and Stale, et al (2014) who reported that laissez-faire leadership was the sole predictor of job satisfaction over a 2-year time lag.

Confirmatory Testing of Hypotheses

Preliminary analysis was conducted in the section above pending for confirmatory testing hypothesis using multiple regression analysis. The multiple regression analysis was conducted to find out whether independent variables transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style, and laissez-faire leadership style together predict dependent variable job satisfaction. Also, the researcher was interested in finding out the best predictor variable (s) of an employee's job satisfaction in the surveyed secondary schools in Monduli district among three predictors. Regression analysis results are given in Table 22, Table 23, and Table 24.

Table 22. Mode Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.480 ^a	0.230	0.212	0.6949

The value of the Adjusted R square in Table 22 was 0.212 which is approximately to 21% amount of variation in job satisfaction explained by the independent variables. The rest 79%

amount of the variation in job satisfaction was explained by other independent variables not considered in the study.

Table 23. Regression Model Summary

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	18.062	3	6.021	12.466	0.000 ^a
	Residual	60.369	125	0.483		
	Total	78.430	128			

ANOVA results in Table 23 give an F statistic = 12.466 and its Sig value of 0.000 which is far less than $\alpha = 0.05$. The computed Sig (0.000) implies that the independent variables contributed

positively significantly to variation in the dependent variable. Also suggests that the model was significantly fit at the 1 % significance level.

Table 24. Regression Coefficient

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.448	0.473		3.061	0.003
Transformational	0.452	0.106	0.314	4.242	0.000
Transactional	0.203	0.105	0.166	1.928	0.056
Laissez-faire	0.073	0.057	-0.102	- 1.293	- 0.198

Table 24 indicates that the computed Sig (p) value for independent transactional leadership style = 0.056 which were greater than a popular Sig = 0.05 suggesting that transactional leadership style was not statistically significantly correlated with job satisfaction at the five percent significance level. Further, Table 4.24 reveals that transformational leadership style and laissez-faire leadership style had Beta values = 0.314 and -0.102 with significance levels of 0.000 and - 0.198 respectively which is less than 0.05, suggesting a statistically significant correlation with dependent variable job satisfaction. Therefore, transformational leadership style and laissez-faire leadership style were found to be predictors of teachers' job satisfaction in the surveyed secondary schools in Monduli district.

Discussion of Study Findings

In this section researcher discusses the findings of the study based on hypothesis by hypothesis.

Hypothesis One

It was first hypothesized that “there is no statistically significant correlation between transformational leadership style and job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district”. Pearson's Linear Correlation Coefficient (PLCC) and multiple regressions were used to determine the relationship between transformational leadership style and teachers' job satisfaction.

The hypothesis was supported by the findings, which were also in line with the findings of earlier studies. For example, Bogler, (2014) study on the influence of leadership style on teacher's job satisfaction found that teacher occupation perception strongly affected their satisfaction. Also, MacMilla (2010) study on the influence of workplace conditions on teacher's job satisfaction in Canada found that workplace conditions positively affected teacher's job satisfaction. Similarly, (Abdullah, 2009) study on job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Tawau, Sabah in Malaysia Relationship between the school principal leadership style and job satisfaction in Serbia, the study found that school principal leadership style influences teacher's satisfaction. (Adjeumo 2012) study on the job satisfaction status of primary school teachers in Ota, Nigeria found that a greater percentage of teachers (52.9%) were satisfied with their job. Further, (Haider 2010) study on the role of transformational and transactional leadership on job satisfaction and career satisfaction found that transformational leadership style and job success are highly related to career satisfaction. (Guiled, 2013) study on leadership styles and job satisfaction empirical evidence from Mogadishu University found a significant relationship between job satisfaction and transformational leadership style. Yushuang, (2013) study on the influence of leadership style on job satisfaction among nurses found that the transformational leadership style contributes more contributing toward job

satisfaction compared to the transactional leadership style.

Emjimofor (2007) studied the relationship between teachers' perceptions of principals' transformational leadership skills and teachers' job satisfaction. Participants were 518 secondary school teachers and 48 principals from two large Local Government Areas in Southeastern Nigeria, found that principals' transformational leadership skills significantly impacted teachers' job satisfaction. Similarly, (Ali and Dahile 2015) investigated the impact of transactional leadership style, transformational and laissez-faire on teacher job satisfaction and found that the three dimensions of leadership style had a significant and positive impact on teacher satisfaction in Secondary school in Mogadishu, Somalia. (Verma, 2014) study on the effect of leadership styles of principals on the job satisfaction of teachers working in private schools in UAE. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant influence of the transformational leadership styles of principals on the job satisfaction of teachers.

Hypothesis Two

The second hypothesis of the study was that, "there is no statistically significant correlation between transactional leadership style and job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district". The hypothesis was supported by the findings. Thus, acceptance of the null hypothesis that there was no statistically significant correlation between transactional leadership style and teacher's job satisfaction, was incongruent with past studies such as (Demissie 2013) relationship between leadership styles of nurse managers and nurses' job satisfaction in Jimma University specialized hospital found that transactional leadership, only contingent reward was found to be statically significant and correlated with extrinsic and intrinsic job satisfaction. Similarly, (Rahim 2014) leadership styles and employees' job Satisfaction of the Private Banking Sector of Pakistan found that there is a significant relationship between transactional leadership style and employees' job satisfaction, and this transactional leadership style is more adopted by leaders as compared to

transformational leadership style. Further, (Waquas, et al. 2012) impact of leadership style (transformational & transactional leadership) on employee performance & mediating role of job satisfaction study of private school (educators) in Pakistan found that transactional and transformational both are significantly and positively associated with Employee performance however transactional leadership was more significant than transformational. (Hlanganipai 2014) study on the impact of leadership styles on employee organizational commitment in higher learning institutions found that transactional leadership style has a significant and positive relationship with only normative commitment. (Afshpour 2014) leadership styles and employees satisfaction, a correlation study in USA found that transactional leadership style has a positive correlation with employee job satisfaction.

Nyenyembe, Malsowski, Nimrod & Peter (2016) study on the relationship between leadership styles applied by school heads and teachers' job satisfaction in Tanzanian secondary schools, the study revealed that teachers were more satisfied with their job when their school heads work closely with them by mentoring them as well as paying attention to their personal well- beings. (Kashagate 2013) study on the effects of leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Musoma Municipal Council, the study examines whether transformational and transactional leadership styles stimulate and sustain teachers' job satisfaction. The results showed that transactional leadership affects the outcome variable, but their influence was lower as compared to the influence of transformational leadership factors. The individual transactional leadership factors that positively influenced the outcome variable were Contingent rewards and active management by exception. (Bass and Avolio 2004) found that transactional leadership can be extremely effective. This study concludes that if teachers and education stakeholders in Monduli district have to increase teachers' job satisfaction special attention should not be directed at transactional leadership style.

Hypothesis Three

The study hypothesized that there is no statistically significant correlation between laissez-faire leadership style and job satisfaction among teachers in selected secondary schools in Monduli district. Data analysis and interpretation using PLCC and multiple regression revealed that there was a significant correlation between laissez-faire leadership style and job satisfaction. This was in agreement with the earlier studies conducted for example (Hassan 2014) test of the impact of leadership styles on employee performance: A study of the Department of Petroleum Resources found that laissez-faire leadership style has tested has a positive relationship on the performance of employees. Moreover, (Stale, et al 2014) the relative effects of constructive, laissez-faire, and tyrannical leadership on subordinate job satisfaction, results from two prospective and representative studies found that laissez-faire leadership was the sole predictor of job satisfaction over a 2-year time lag. (Adeyemi 2010) leadership style and job satisfaction in Nigerian schools found that there was no significant relationship between principals' laissez-faire leadership style and teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. (Dalhie 2015) leadership and leaders' job satisfaction in Somalia secondary schools found that laissez-faire had a significant and positive impact on teacher's satisfaction in secondary schools in Mogadishu, Somalia.

Conclusion

The following conclusions are hereby derived from the findings of the three hypotheses:

1. The transformational leadership style was an essential leadership style to increase employee job satisfaction in the selected secondary schools in Monduli district. Therefore, head teachers in the selected secondary schools should embrace the transformational leadership style as it has been found to have a great influence on employee job satisfaction.

2. The transactional leadership style was not important in influencing teachers' job satisfaction levels in the selected secondary schools in Monduli district. Hence transactional leadership style could not be given much attention.

3. Laissez-faire leadership style was important in influencing teachers' job satisfaction in the surveyed secondary schools in Monduli district. Therefore the head teachers should put into consideration the laissez-faire leadership style as it had a great influence on teachers' job satisfaction in surveyed secondary schools in Monduli district.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are hereby suggested with respect to the three hypotheses:

1. The secondary school administration should focus on transformational leadership style since it was found to be a predictor of teachers' job satisfaction in the surveyed secondary school in Monduli district. If the secondary schools administrators are to increase teachers job satisfaction should be given the upper hand.

2. Heads of schools should understand that however much the leadership style is important it was found that had no significant correlation with teacher's job satisfaction. Therefore, much emphasis should not be directed on transactional leadership style if is to increase teachers' job satisfaction since it was found.

3. The secondary schools administration should focus on laissez-faire leadership style since it was found to be a predictor of teacher's job satisfaction the surveyed secondary school in Monduli district. If the secondary schools administrators are to increase teachers job satisfaction should be given the high attention.

References

Abdullah, M.M., Uli, J. S & Parasusaman, B (2009). Job satisfaction among the secondary

- school teachers in Tawau Sabah in Malaysia. *Montenegrin Journal of Economics*, 10(1) 43-45.
- Adeyemi, T.O & Bolarinmwa, R (2010) leadership style and job satisfaction in Nigerian School. *International Journal of Management and Transformation*, 7(2). <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v8n13p34>
- Addejumo, G.O., & Gesinde, A.M. (2012). Job satisfaction status of primary school teachers in Ota Nigeria. *European Journal of Educational Studies*, 4(1).
- Afshipour, S. (2014) Leadership styles and employees satisfaction, a correlation study in USA. *International Letters of Social and Human Sciences*, 27, 156-169. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18052/www.scipress.com/ILSHS.27.156>
- Akhtar, S. & Iqbal, A. (2010). Job satisfaction of secondary school teachers. *Abasyn Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(1).
- Ali, A. Y. S. & Dahie, M. A. (2015). Leadership style and teachers job satisfaction: Empirical survey from secondary schools in Somalia. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 5(8), 84-96.
- Amin, M. E. (2005). *Foundations of statistical inference for social research*. Kampala, Makerere University Printery
- Bass, B. (2009). *The Bass handbook of leadership: Theory, research, and managerial applications* (4th ed.). New York, NY: Free Press
- Bass, B. M. & Avolio, B. J. (2004). *MLQ: Multifactor leadership questionnaire*. 2nd edition, Technical report. Redwood city, CA: Mind Garden
- Bass, B. M. (1998). *Transformational leadership: Industry, military, and educational impact*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Bass, B.M. (1990). From transactional to transformation-al leadership: Learning to share the vision. *Organizational Dynamics*, 18(3), 19-31. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0090-2616\(90\)90061-S](https://doi.org/10.1016/0090-2616(90)90061-S)
- Bogler, R. (2014). The influence of leadership style on teacher's job satisfaction. *The Journal of leadership for effective and equitable organizations*, 37(5), 662-683. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/00131610121969460>
- Brymer, E., & Gray, T. (2006). Effective leadership: Transformational or transactional? *Australian Journal of Outdoor Education*, 10(2), 13-19. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF03400835>
- Burns, J. M. (1978). *Leadership*. New York, NY: Harper and Row.
- Christen, M., Lyre, G., & Soberman, D. (2006). Job satisfaction, job performance, and effort: Are examination using agency theory. *Journal of Marketing*, 70(1), 137-150. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.2006.70.1.137>
- Dalhie, M. A. & Ali, S. V.A (2015) Leadership style and teacher job satisfaction: Empirical survey from secondary school in Somalia. *Research on Human and Social Science*, 5(8).
- Demissie, N. & Nagussie, A. (2013). Relationship between leadership styles of nurse managers and nurses' job satisfaction in Jimma University Specialized Hospital. *Ethiopian Journal of Health Science*, 23(1), 49-58
- Ejimofor, F.O. (2007). *Principles transformational leadership skills and their teacher job satisfaction in Nigeria*. University of Nigeria
- Field, D. L., & Herold, D. M. (1997). Using the leadership practices inventory to measure transformational and transactional leadership. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 57, 569-580. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164497057004003>
- Guiled, S. H., Sidow, A.M & Ali, S. Y. A (2013) Leadership styles and job satisfaction. *European Journal of Management Sciences and Economic*, 1(1).
- Haider, H, M, & Riaz, A. (2016). Role of transformational and transactional leadership on job satisfaction and career satisfaction found that transformational leadership style and job success are highly related with career satisfaction. *Business and Economic Horizons*, 1(1), 29-38. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15208/beh.2010.05>

- Hamidifar, F. (2010). *A study of the relationship between leadership styles and employee job satisfaction*. Islamic Azad University Branches in Tehran, Iran.
- Hassan, B. A. & Obasana, K.L. (2014). Test of the impact of leadership styles on employee performance: A study of department of petroleum resources. *International Journal of Management Sciences*, 2(4), 149-160.
- Hlanganipai, N. & Wiza, M. (2014). The impact of leadership styles on employee organisational commitment in higher learning institutions. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(4), 135. <https://doi.org/10.5901/MJSS.2014.V5N4P135>
- House, R. J. (1968). Leadership training: Some dysfunctional consequences. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 12, 556- 571. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2391533>
- Huberts, L. W., Kaptein, M., & Lasthuizen, K. (2007). A study of the impact of three leadership styles on integrity violations committed by police officers. *Policing: An International Journal of Police Strategies & Management*, 30(4), 587-607.
- Jones, G.R. and George, J.M. (2004). *Essentials of Contemporary Management*. McGraw Hill Companies, Inc., Boston.
- Karanja, G. W., Mugwe, J. N., & wanderi, P. G. (2013). *Effects of leadership style on job satisfaction of teachers: a survey of secondary schools in DundoriZo*.
- Kashagate, R. (2013). *Influence of leadership style on teachers' job satisfaction In Tanzania: The case of public secondary schools in Musoma Municipal Council*. Mzumbe University.
- Krejciec, R. V. & Morgan, D. (1970). Determine sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30, 607-610. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001316447003000308>
- Lim, S. (2008). Job satisfaction of information technology workers in academic libraries. *Library & Information Science Research*, 30(2), 115-121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LISR.2007.10.002>
- Lund, D.L. (2003). Organizational culture and job satisfaction. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 18(3), 219–236. <https://doi.org/10.1108/0885862031047313>
- MacMillan, B. R & Maxin (2010). Influence of workplace condition on teacher's job satisfaction Canada. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 93(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220679909597627>
- McMillan, J. H. & Schumacher, S. (2006). *Research in education: Evidence based inquiry* (6th ed.) Pearson Education Inc.
- Mullins, L. J. (2010). *Management and Organizational Behaviour* (9th Ed.). London: Pearson Education Limited.
- Nguni, S., Slegers, P., & Denessen, E. (2006). Transformational and transactional leadership effects on teachers' job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and organizational citizenship behavior in primary schools: The Tanzanian case. *School Effectiveness and School improvement*, 17(2), 145-177. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243450600565746>
- Northouse, P. (2013). *Leadership: Theory and practice* (6th ed.). Los Angeles, CA: Sage
- Northouse, P.G., 2010. *Leadership: Theory and Practice*. (5th Ed), SAGE Publications, California.
- Nyenyembe, F. W., Malsowski, R., Nimrod, S. B. & Peter, L. (2016). Leadership styles and teachers' Job satisfaction in Tanzania n Public Secondary Schools. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 4(5), 980-988. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2016.040507>
- Okumbe, J.A. (1998). *Educational management theory and practice*. Nairobi: Nairobi University Press.
- Pearce, C. L., & Sims, H. P. (2002). Transactors, transformers and beyond: a multi-method development of a theoretical typology of leadership. *Journal of Management Development*, 22(1), 273-307. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/02621710310467587>
- Pihie, Z. A. L., Sadeghi, A., & Elias, H. (2011). Analysis of heads of departments' leadership styles: Implication for improving Research University management practice. *Procedia Social*

and Behavioral Sciences, 29(2011), 1081–1090.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.11.341>

Rahim, M., Jaffari, A. A. & Javed, A. H. (2014). Leadership styles and employees' job Satisfaction: A case from the Private Banking Sector of Pakistan. *Journal of Asian Business Strategy*.

Riaz, A., & Haider, M. H. (2010). Role of transformational and transactional leadership on job satisfaction and career satisfaction. *Business and Economic Horizons*, 1(1), 29–38.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.15208/beh.2010.05>

Robbins, S.P., Decenzo, D. A. & M. Coulter, (2010). *Fundamentals of Management: Essential Concepts and Applications* (7th Ed), Prentice Hall, New Jersey.

Sarantakos, S. (2001). *Social research*. Palgrave Publishers Ltd.

Schilling, J. (2009). From ineffectiveness to destruction: A qualitative study on the meaning of negative leadership. *Leadership*, 5(1), 102–129.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1742715008098312>

Spector, P. E. (1997). *Job satisfaction: Application, assessment, cause, and consequences*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Stale, et al (2014) The relative effects of constructive, laissez-faire, and tyrannical leadership on subordinate job satisfaction: Results from two prospective and representative

studies. *Zeitschrift für Psychologie*, 222(4), 221-232.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1027/2151-2604/a000189>

Teshome, Y. (2008). *Challenges of Higher Education in Africa and Lessons of Experience for the Africa-U.S. Higher Education Collaboration Initiative*. National Association of State Universities and Land-Grant Colleges. Washington D.C

Verman, N. (2014). The influence of leadership styles of Principals on Teachers' job satisfaction in private schools in UAE. *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 1(3).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.31920/2633-2930/2022/v3n3a8>

Wahab, J. A., Fuad, C. F. M., Ismail, A, H. & Majid, S. (2014). Headmasters' transformational leadership and their relationship with teachers' job Satisfaction and teachers' commitments. *International Education Studies*; 7(13).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ies.v7n13p40>

Waquas, H. et al., (2012). Impact of leadership style (transformational & transactional leadership) on employee performance & mediating role of job satisfaction study of private school (educator) in Pakistan. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 12(4).

Yushuang, T., Rahman, A. G. A., Noos, H, Adi, M. N. M & Ahmad, R. A. (2013). The influence of leadership style on job satisfaction. *Asian Journal Science*, 9(9).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ass.v9n9p172>